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INCREASING EFFICIENCY OF CATERING ENTERPRISES THROUGH MODERNIZATION

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Abstract: This article examines how, in the conditions of the digital economy, the material and technical support of enterprises in the service sector becomes important for the accelerated development of this sphere, especially in meeting the needs of people. They differ in the types, sizes and level of services provided. However, not all meet the requirements of the period. Therefore, it is necessary to improve the technical and technological modernization of enterprises in the service sector.

The article develops a method for determining the technical and economic level of service enterprises based on the technical and functional indicators of their service at enterprises.

Key words: Modernization of enterprises, technical level, technical and economic level, new equipment, renewal of fixed assets, efficiency, service.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida xizmat ko'rsatish korxonalarining moddiy texnika bilan ta'minlanganligi ushbu sohani jadal rivojlantirishda, ayniqsa, insonlar ehtiyojlarini qondirishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etish masalalari ko'rib chiqilgan. Xizmat ko'rsatish korxonalarida xizmat ko'rsatishning texnikaviy va funksional ko'rsatkichlaridan kelib chiqib, ularning texnikaviy-iqtisodiy darajasini aniqlash metodi ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: korxonalarni modernizatsiya, texnikaviy daraja, texnik – iqtisodiy daraja, yangi texnika, asosiy fondlarining yangilanishi, samaradorlik, xizmat ko'rsatish.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается вопрос о том, как в условиях цифровой экономики материально-техническое обеспечение предприятий сферы услуг приобретает важное значение для ускоренного развития этой сферы, особенно в удовлетворении потребностей людей. Они различаются между собой по типам, размерам и уровню предоставляемых услуг. Однако не все соответствуют требованиям периода. Поэтому необходимо совершенствовать технико-технологическую модернизацию предприятий сферы услуг.

В статье разработан метод определения технико-экономического уровня предприятий сферы услуг на основе технико-функциональных показателей их обслуживания на предприятиях.

Ключевые слова: модернизация предприятий, технический уровень, технико-экономический уровень, новое оборудование, обновление основных фондов, эффективность, сервис.

INTRODUCTION

In the world, it is envisaged that the development of catering enterprises, first of all, will be prepared on the basis of a special technology of nutrition, the development of means of communication, means of conveying raw materials and products, technical and technological updating of production processes. In this respect, it is one of the important tasks to carry out targeted scientific research on the modernization of catering enterprises, improving the quality of Service.

It is known that the modernization of enterprises requires, first of all, to improve the quality of products, expand the range, standards meet requirements, improve working conditions and improve the qualifications of employees. To do this, it is necessary to consistently strengthen the material and technical base of the enterprise, including replacing the techniques and technologies that are considered its foundation with modern types with high economic indicators from time to time. Naturally, in such a situation, the question "what exactly do they need to update?" is a rightful question. We offer to determine its technical economic level at the enterprise on the basis of existing techniques and technologies. Because the main part of the material and technical base of the enterprise is the technical economic level, which expands its assortment, satisfies standard requirements, improves working conditions, requires highly qualified workers. Modernization of the enterprise means, first of all, innovation to its production, that is, the introduction of new techniques. At the same time, various techniques and equipment are used in catering enterprises in our country. It is important to define the directions of development of these branches by technical-technological modernization, both scientific-theoretical and methodological. Consequently, this issue is one of the pressing problems that must be studied.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Problems of modernization of catering enterprises, as well as improving its efficiency S.M.Yampolsky, S.G.Galuza, V.I.Economists of foreign countries such as terekhin, A.V.Vakhabov, B.A.Abdukarimov, D.X.Aslanova, R.A.Seytmuratov

Analysis of the topic used analysis and synthesis, induction and deduction, a systematic approach, logical and comparative methods of analysis, statistical and econometric modeling, sociological survey methods.

DISCUSSION

The services provided at service enterprises in our country are an important aspect of the economy, which is engaged in by many organizations and individual business entities. The development of Service Enterprises has the task of meeting the needs of people in a variety of ways. A special role in the implementation of such tasks is played by the modernization of service enterprises. However, not all of them are in modern demand.

V.I.Terexin ^[1] believes that this issue is considered in various methods modeled in industrial enterprises with high capacity. The same asno is considered as a multi-parameter function to the technical level of the product. That is, the technical level of the j -product is represented by indicators Xi (i=1,n)

$$K_{i\sigma_j} = \varphi(x'_{ij}; x'_{i\sigma}; a_i)$$

In this: $x'_{i\sigma}$ – i- indicator base value;

a_i – i – indicator value (salinity).

When assessing the technical and economic level, additional economic indicators should also be taken into account. Then its quotient can be expressed as:

$$K_{i\sigma} = \psi(x'_{ij}; x'_{i\sigma}; 3_{ij}; 3_{i\sigma}),$$

In this: 3_{ij} – l costs in the industry. (l=1,l)

From this mathematical model, it can be seen that the technical level and the technical and economic level are not mutually opposed, but complement each other. Therefore, we consider it permissible to use both models in assessing the innovation novelty of the enterprise inherent in time. Because the technical level indicates how well the equipment of the enterprise has been improved, the technical and economic level will directly depend on the profitability of the enterprise.

We propose to calculate the following holistic method using methods for calculating the effectiveness of the introduction of new (innovation) techniques into the enterprise, mainly in the industry: ^[3]

1. The material and technical base of the enterprise (main fund)ning technician-economist during a detailed analysis of the situation;
2. Zoning of functional groups of the material and technical base (main fund) of the enterprise and collecting information about them;
3. Each functional group trains Ktd to obtain accurate and instructional knowledge of mathematicians, specialists of the feasibility study of the enterprise.:

$$K_{\sigma\delta\alpha} = \left[\frac{\sum_{n=i}^i K_{\sigma\delta\alpha ij}}{n} \right]$$

Where: n is the number of groups;

4. $\overline{K_{\sigma\delta\alpha ij}}$ – the average value of the Ktd of the computational object (technique, equipment, etc.) in each group is:

$$K_{\kappa m \delta} = \left[\frac{\sum_{n=i}^i K_{m \delta i s}}{n} \right]$$

Where: n is the number of objects in the same group.

$K_{\tau\delta i s}$ – coefficient of technical level of objects (equipment, equipment, etc.).

$$K_{\text{tdij}} - \text{to calculate } K_{\text{d}\bar{i}} = \sum_{i=1}^n a_i \cdot P_i$$

the formula is chosen, and here is the coefficient of salinity of the parameter – I;

-i – the basal value of the parameter;

$$\text{for scaling } a_{ir} = \gamma \frac{x'_{ir}}{x'_{il}} a_{il}$$

In this case – γ the coefficient of recalculation of the general assessment to find the value of the technical level real (Ktd*)

If in most cases $\gamma = 1$ and then $K \text{ td} = K^* \text{ td}$

$$a_{ir} = \gamma \frac{x'_{ir}}{x'_{il}} a_{il}$$

the formula, that is, the calculation of the object (zhihozlar and bashkalara)ning the main course of calculations.

5. The efficiency of the economics of new technology.

The technical and economic level of service enterprises during the modernization period was determined. In particular, in the analysis of the main funds of the Samarkand City restaurant “star”, functional groups on the method of determining the technical and economic level of the enterprise depending on the tasks of organizing the realization and consumption of products in their production process: 1. Production equipment; 2. Furniture and inventory; 3. Buildings and structures; 4. Allocated to other equipment and inventories. Likewise, depending on which process the functional of the group of production equipment performs: 1. Mechanical equipment; 2. Heating equipment; 3. Cooling equipment; 4. The coolant was divided into a group of equipment. [4]. In this case, the innovation in each group was calculated in the proposed method of updating and selected by comparing the technical and economic level. The update of the equipment used in the Samarkand City restaurant “star” was considered on the example of the choice of frityurnisa, which is a thermal unit in it.

The equipment of frityurnisa, which worked at the enterprise, was compared with the new ones. In this case, the selected indicators of the equipment being calculated were perceived as having the same salinity, and the salinity coefficient was calculated on the indicators of equipment 1 and 2 bases (working at the enterprise) (Table 1).

Table 1: Calculation of the technical and economic level of thermal equipment based on the variable base of the Samarkand City restaurant “Star”¹

Equipment		Specification				Technical and economic level coefficient			
		X1 kg / hour	X2, kWt	X3, kg	X4, m 2	On base 1	On base 2	Under Base 1 Condition 2 a	Under Base 2 condition 1 a
A	Electrophritiurnisa ФЭСМ-20	20	7,5	9,0	0,36	1	2,52	0,9	2,28
B	Frityurnisa ФЭСМ-16	16	6	18	0,2	0,57	1,5	0,7	1,49
Base									
1	ФЭСМ-20	20	7,5	90	0,36				
2	ФНЭ-5	8	4	25	0,11				
	By specification salinity coefficient	0,25	0,25	0,25	0,25	For all			
		0,13	0,69	0,07	0,09	1 base for 2 Base conditions			
		0,14	0,44	0,21	0,19	2 for 1 base conditions			

Here: x1 – equipment productivity, kg / h; x2-electrodvigateli capacity, kW; x3-mass, kg; X4-place of occupancy, m².

The results of the analysis showed that under the same conditions, fsem-20 indicators from both base equipment were found to consume more energy. But, although the coolness of the same equipment indicators has almost the same productivity when comparing koeffi-tsients, its weight (metal capacity) is almost 10 times

1 Formed on the basis of the author's research.

less than the space occupied. With the same base of the newly proposed FESM-20 $K_{tid2} = 1$ it can be seen that. But, from the second on the base $K_{tid2} = 2,52$ fold larger. Similarly ФЭСМ-16, ФЭСМ-20 less than $K_{tid2} = 0,57$, ФНЭ-5 while $K_{tid2} = 1,5$ we can see the magnitude of. If, under the condition of Base 2 on base 1, which is in production, it is clear that, more precisely, the latter is superior to equipment A ($K_{tid2} = 0,9$), while considering its (ФНЭ-5) conditions, even if it is outdated ($K_{tid2} = 0,7$).

Similarly, it was noted that under the terms of Base 2, Base 1 (similar to itself, produced only earlier in the Year account), their feasibility level was higher: $K_{tid2} = 2,28$, $K_{tid2} = 1,49$. On the basis of this method, other equipment available at the enterprise was also calculated, and their average technical and economic level ($K_{tid2} = 1,7$) was determined.

RESULTS

From the results of the calculations, it turns out that in order to raise the quality of service at the enterprise, it is necessary to replace mechanical equipment and cooling apparatus that hang in production with modern ones. Because their technical and economic level is lower than that of other groups. Economic efficiency, on the other hand, depends on the modernization of the technical economic level of the enterprise. With an average coefficient of technical economic level of the enterprise of 1.34, its economic efficiency is 670 thousand rubles.

CONCLUSION

In order to accelerate the modernization of service, service enterprises, to introduce innovations, proposals were developed to determine the technical and economic level of enterprises. It was confirmed that the equipment of service enterprises in the Samarkand region should be replaced with the necessary modern types.

Proposals have been developed to improve the efficiency of the service enterprise through the selection, replacement of new equipment, based on the factors affecting the innovation activity of the service enterprise and the technical and economic level of the enterprise. As a result, the correlation of the technical and economic level of service enterprises in the Samarkand region with its economic efficiency was substantiated.

Consequently, the economic efficiency of the enterprise is greatly influenced by the technical level of technological equipment used in its production. Therefore, all equipment must be in a state of good condition, in accordance with the operating regulations, they must be provided with technical services from time to time, and the old ones must be replaced with new ones.

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